

PEOPLE PERCEPTION TOWARDS 'MAKE IN INDIA' CONCEPT: RESPONSES FROM URBAN RESIDENTS OF KOLKATA.

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ABSTRACT

Indian Government launched its 'Make in India' project on 25th September, 2014. It is no denying fact that India becomes a hotspot destination for the foreign investors by virtue of this project. Domestic organizations are also in a hurry to utilize the benefits of the project and give back something good to the society. After adoption of new industrial policy in 1991, Indian economy took a rocket boost in every sector. Main aim of promoting this project is to attract as many companies to start their ventures in India. This project is really helpful for the generation of more number of employments in our country. But do people aware about the 'Make in India' term? What are the thinking and attitude towards the project? Especially when 'Made in India' concept is already in existence from independence. Do people know the difference between 'Made in India' and 'Make in India'? It is true that after independence 'Made in India' project help to develop a stronger economy and proper use of human resources. Still there is an urgent need of a new project which will supplement it. "Make in India" is one of that kind. This paper is meant for examining the people perception of 'Make in India', from their desire to know, willingness to participate, attitude, and reactions towards it.

Key words: Make in India, Made in India, People perception, Attitudes and reactions.

INTRODUCTION

Government of India initiated 'Make in India' program on 25th September 2014 and the program was inaugurated by the Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi. 'Make in India' campaign aimed to encourage multinational and domestic companies for direct investment and manufacturing of products and goods in India.

India is well known for its offering of services in different fields across the globe. 'Make in India' campaign concentrates on twenty five different sectors of Indian economy for creation of new jobs. It also gives priority to skill development.

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Few of the sectors are information technology, manufacturing, automobiles, chemicals, textiles, ports, aviation, pharmaceuticals, tourism, leather, hospitality, railways, renewal energy, mining etc. It has been expected that 'Make in India' program will be able to attract foreign capital as well as technological investments in India.

MAKE IN INDIA

The 'Make in India' concept / program focuses on manufacturing sector with "Zero defect, Zero effect" slogan coined by Prime minister of India. The program aims that there will be no export return of manufacturing goods.

'Make in India' campaign comes with a new logo (lion), a new website, and full page advertisement in national and regional newspapers. The main objective is to generate employment by establishing new manufacturing units in India.

MADE IN INDIA

Made in India program was adopted post independence to build and develop different industrial sectors. The main aim of 'Made in India' program was to encourage foreign and domestic organizations to develop and manufacture products domestically.

'Made in India' campaign was very much successful till the New Industrial Policy (1991) comes into effect.

PEOPLE PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE

People perception generally refers to how and why an individual initiates and sustains certain behavior. People perception is based on sensation or exposure on which an individual gets exposed.

People attitude is also influenced largely by their perceptual selectivity. Perceptual selectivity is a process by which they give a meaning to it. Indian people are perceptually very sensitive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to NalinRai (The Better India Reader, your view: "Make in India" to Make A Better India, 2014 www.thebetterindia.com) the 'Make in India' is creating a whole new brand identity for India. The lion icon chosen to represent the 'Make in India' is very successful to attract the attention of the mass.

GunjanBhagowaty (2014) published a research paper on different aspects of 'Make in India'. Bhagowaty also discussed about the different challenges of practical implementation of Make in India concept and also offered possible solutions to it. Researcher also raises several feasibility issues of 'Make in India' concept to the root level.

SamridhiGoyal et al. (2015) in a research emphasizes the role of human resources and financial services in making 'Make in India' campaign successful. Researcher also suggested that there are needs for reforms in different industrial strategies to guarantee the success of 'Make in India' campaign.

Researcher Russel (2014) raised questions about 'Make in India' campaign that it can generate jobs in manufacturing sector or not. Russel also pointed that formal manufacturing sectors are real growth sector in India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To find out peoples familiarity with the 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' program.
2. To find out people awareness of the perspectives (differences) of 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' concept.
3. To find out peoples trust on 'Make in India' program as a catalyst to boost Indian economic growth.
4. To find out peoples belief on 'Make in India' campaign to attract foreign investment.
5. To assess people's belief that 'Make in India' campaign will create more job opportunities.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

1. H0: There are no differences between the people's age and familiarity with 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' campaign.
H1: There are differences between the people's age and familiarity with 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' campaign.
2. H0: There are no differences between the people's age with awareness of differences (perspective) of 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' campaign.
H1: There are differences between the people's age with awareness of differences (perspectives) of 'Make in India' and 'Made in India' campaign.

METHODOLOGY

This study was done by taking into account both primary and secondary data.

Primary Data: Primary data was collected with the help of a self completion questionnaire with literate persons who are urban residents belonging to various areas of Kolkata. 72 of such persons completed the questionnaire.

Response Rate and Sample Description: A self completion questionnaire was given to 80 literate urban residents of different parts of Kolkata. Out of which only 72 literate residents completed the questionnaire.

Secondary Data: It was collected from different articles, journals, books and internet etc.

Sampling Type: Convenience sampling method was used.

Analytical Tool Used: Number method and Chi square test.

Period of Study: Data collection took approximately six months.

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

The demographic profiles of the literate urban respondents of Kolkata took part in the survey process are given below in table number 1.

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

Table No. – 1

Age in years	Number of Respondents
20-29	42
30-39	30
Sex	Number of Respondents
Male	45
Female	27
Occupation	Number of Respondents
Student	20
Business	15
Service	21
Homemaker	16
Education	Number of Respondents
10 th Std	12
12 th Std	25
Graduate	27
Post Graduate	8

FINDINGS

From table number 2 it has been clear that:

- Out of 72 respondents 48 literate urban respondents of Kolkata city are familiar with 'Make in India' campaign.
- Out of 72 respondents 45 literate urban respondents of Kolkata city are aware about the differences of perspectives of 'Make in India' campaign.
- Out of 72 respondents 39 literate urban respondents of Kolkata city believes that 'Make in India' will boost Indian economic growth.
- Out of 72 respondents 29 literate urban respondents of Kolkata city believes that 'Make in India' will attract foreign companies to invest in India.
- Out of 72 respondents 31 literate urban respondents of Kolkata city believes that 'Make in India' will create more job opportunities in India.

Questions (Table No. – 2)	Response from literate urban residents of Kolkata	
	Make in India	
Familiarity with the campaign	Yes	No
	48	24
Awareness about the differences of perspectives of	Yes	No
	45	27
Beliefs that Make in India will boost Indian economic growth	Yes	No
	39	33
Make in India will attract foreign companies to invest in India	Yes	No
	29	43
Make in India will create more job opportunities in India	Yes	No
	31	41

RESULT

From table 3 it has been clear that:

Familiarity with the campaign (Table No.: 3)										
Age in years	Make in India		Chi-square statistic	p-value <0.05	Remarks	Made in India		Chi-square statistic	p-value <0.05	Remarks
	Yes	No				Yes	No			
20-29	30	12	1.028	0.310	H1: Rejected	18	24	8.159	0.0042	H1: Accepted
30-39	18	12				23	7			
Awareness about the differences of perspectives of										
Age in years	Make in India		Chi-square statistic	p-value <0.05	Remarks	Made in India		Chi-square statistic	p-value <0.05	Remarks
	Yes	No				Yes	No			
20-29	28	14	0.746	0.387	H1: Rejected	19	23	4.345	0.0371	H1: Accepted
30-39	17	13				21	9			

People Perception Towards 'Make in India' Concept: Responses from Urban Residents of Kolkata.

- There are no differences between the people's age and familiarity with 'Make in India' campaign.
- There are differences between the people's age and familiarity with 'Made in India' campaign.
- There are no differences between the people's age with awareness of perspective of 'Make in India' campaign.
- There are differences between the people's age with awareness of perspective of 'Made in India' campaign.

LIMITATIONS

1. The population was limited to the literate urban residents of Kolkata city only.
2. Respondents may have their own biasness towards the campaigns.
3. Convenience sampling method has been used; generalization needs to be done cautiously.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates few key points. Firstly, younger generation literate respondents from Kolkata belonging to age group 20-29 years are familiar with 'Make in India' concept but lacks in terms of erstwhile 'Made in India' concept. While respondents belong to age group 30-39 years are familiar with both 'Made in India' and 'Make in India' concept. Secondly, there is not much difference in terms of knowledge about the differences of the above mentioned two concepts among two age groups. Thirdly, very few respondents of Kolkata beliefs that 'Make in India' will boost Indian economic growth. Fourthly, less number of respondents from Kolkata trusts that 'Make in India' will attract foreign companies to invest in India. Lastly, small number of respondent's from Kolkata admits that 'Make in India' will create more job opportunities in India.

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